

The Mosque Cluster at Gedi

also known as "The Mosque Cluster at Gede", "Gedi Mosques"

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The Gedi mosques are a group of religious structures located in the heart of ancient Swahili city of Gedi, also known as Gede. Gedi was likely occupied between the 11th and 17th centuries CE, and was a typical Swahili "stone town" located on the East African coast in modern Kenya. The ruins of Gedi include a walled town and its suburbs. The main built area consists of houses, a palace, and some mosques. Two of these mosques have been identified as "Great Mosques" by Pradines (2003). Open areas in the settlement have been identified as zones where structures constructed of perishable materials were located. Like most of the surviving structures at Gedi, the mosques were constructed using coral limestone extracted from the Indian Ocean and cemented with mud-lime mortar. Foundations tend to be about a foot deep and not much wider than the walls they support. The mosques and other structures were built along a planned grid. The mosques are associated with wells and washing facilities for use before (and after?) worship. The mosques are not associated with minarets, breaking with common practice elsewhere in the Muslim world. This could be due to Ibadi influence in the region. Gedi's mosques were planned with anterooms flanking a central chamber. The roof of the mosques were likely supported by wood beams and square stone pillars. The largest mosque at Gedi has three entrances and three rows of square stone pillars. Breaking with the generally aniconic decoration of Swahili mosques, this mosque has a relief of a spear placed next to a shield on its spandrel above one of its entrances. The east entrance's architrave is decorated with a geometric herringbone pattern. All the mosques of Gedi have a decorated mihrab on their north walls, the direction of Mecca. The second largest mosque of the city seems to be older than its larger counterpart. This second mosque was constructed in the 12th century before being reconstructed and expanded in the 13th and 14th centuries. This second mosque measure 26m in length, north to south. Like many mosques of medieval Swahili settlements, the mosques of Gedi are associated with tombs constructed of limestone, mortar, and plaster. These tombs often are constructed with pillars topping them. These tombs are constructed with recessed decorative panels. There are four large pillar tombs at Gedi, but only one is dated by an inscription - 1399CE.

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1650 CE

Region: Gedi

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Kenya, Gedi

The location of the ancient city of Gedi, Kenya.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Pradines, S. (2003). Islamization and urbanization on the coast of East Africa: Recent excavations at Gedi, Kenya. *Azania: Archaeological Research in Africa*, 38(1), 180-182.
- Source 2: Pradines, S. (2019). La bipartition des cités swahili: l'exemple de Gedi (Kenya). *Studies in the African Past*, 2, 66-75.
- Source 3: Bita, Caesar, and Wes Forsythe. "An Outport for Gedi?—Archaeological Survey in Mida Creek, Kenya." *Heritage* 6.12 (2023): 7366-7380.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://zamaniproject.org/site-kenya-gede-ruins.html#header7-h9>
- Source 1 Description: Zamani Project's 3D documentation of Gedi

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Systematic scientific excavations began at Gedi in the 1940s under the direction of James Kirkman. Excavations have continued into the 21st century. A recent proposal was put to the NSF to conduct Lidar surveys of Gedi and its environs to properly map the site and understand its spatial layout.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1948-present

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Multiple excavations have taken place at Gedi

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Other [specify]: The site of Gedi is located in the Arabuko-Sokoke Forest. It also has multiple wells

associated with it.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature

Notes: The ground was leveled before the city grid was planned. The surrounding forest was cleared and kept at bay while the city was occupied. Multiple trackways lead through the city. There are multiple wells located within Gedi.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: But the site was an urban center between the 12th and 17th centuries CE.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: The site is currently located in the Arabuko-Sokoke Forest, close to some small settlements.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The mosques of Gedi were built in close association with the city of Gedi.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: There are multiple wells associated with the mosques

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple mosques associated with the city of Gedi. The city is composed of a palace, mosques, and houses, all built of limestone.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple mosques, wells, and trackways associated with the site

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: There are multiple wells and roads associated with the mosques.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The mosques are part of the larger city of Gedi

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Islamic worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Both communal and individual Muslim worship

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The second largest mosque in particular was expanded twice in the 13th and 14th centuries after its initial construction in the 12th century.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: The mosques lie in ruin today, with their roofs collapsed and walls crumbling.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: It seems that the ravages of time did the most damage to the mosques of Gedi. However, there are local stories of the city being raided by the Wazimba people in 1589, in addition to evidence of Oromo migration and raids from Somalia.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: It seems that the ravages of time did the most damage to the mosques of Gedi. However, there are local stories of the city being raided by the Wazimba people in 1589, in addition to evidence of Oromo migration and raids from Somalia.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The site was not reinhabited after its abandonment in the early 17th century CE.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is entirely possible that the mosques were partly given over to communication with non-human supernatural beings. However, it seems that the mosques were constructed in theory to be in service to Islamic orthodoxy and orthopraxy.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is entirely possible that the mosques were partly given over to the worship of a semi-divine human being. However, it seems that the mosques were constructed in theory to be in service to Islamic orthodoxy and orthopraxy.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is entirely possible that the mosques were partly given over to the worship/veneration of non-divine ancestors. In many caves in East Africa, ancestor spirits in the form of pythons are venerated. However, it seems that the mosques were constructed in theory to be in service to Islamic orthodoxy and orthopraxy.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Notes: Most likely, the rulers of Gedi or powerful local families that derived their wealth from the Indian Ocean trade network commissioned the construction of the mosques.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Notes: Local Swahili elites likely commissioned the mosques. However, whether they were built by dedicated priests, slaves, corvee laborers, indentured servants, captured enemies, men, women, or children is unknown. Specialist architects likely took part in the construction of the mosque.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Notes: The place may have already been sacred in pre-Islamic East African religious traditions. It is unknown, however, whether the mosques were constructed due to divine intervention.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– I don't know

Notes: The place may have already been sacred in pre-Islamic East African religious traditions. It is unknown, however, whether the mosques were constructed to commemorate the birthplace of supernatural or human being.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Notes: The place may have already been sacred in pre-Islamic East African religious traditions. It is unknown, however, whether the mosques were constructed due to the result of a specific event.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: The site was likely constructed by local elites as conspicuous and competitive acts of piety.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The place may have already been sacred in pre-Islamic East African religious traditions. It is unknown, however, why the mosques were constructed when and where they were.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Quran (likely)

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether texts were located in the mosques is unknown.

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– No

Notes: The mosques are no longer in use.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The mosques are associated with wells and washing areas, and are located in the heart of the city of Gedi.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The mosques are located within the city of Gedi, but may not be physically attached to each other and other structures.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: Two mosques in particular have been identified as "Great Mosques", with one of these larger than the others.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: But the largest mosque runs 28m north to south

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Limestone and shells were burned to produce plaster.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: The limestone seems to have been sourced from the shore, which lies a couple of km away.

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: A large forest abuts Gedi.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Coral limestone was used to construct the mosques and other structures at Gedi.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Plaster was made by burning limestone and shells.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

Notes: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

Notes: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's

architrave.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave. These are visible to all visitors to the mosque

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: In accordance with Islamic practice, no statues are present. However, there is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Notes: But, There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Notes: But, There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque. This could be a reference to a story now forgotten.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Notes: But, there is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque. These could be representative of a now-forgotten narrative.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a spear and shield located on one of the spandrels of the largest mosque, in addition to a herringbone pattern located on the east entrance's architrave.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: But there are Muslim tombs, pillar tombs in particular, associated with these mosques.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that worship of the dead not associated with orthodox Islamic practice took place. However, the lack of texts associated with these mosques makes it impossible to definitively answer this question.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that treatment of corpses not associated with orthodox Islamic practice took place. However, the lack of texts associated with these mosques makes it impossible to definitively answer this question.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– I don't know

Notes: None that have survived archaeologically. Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that co-sacrifices not associated with orthodox Islamic practice took place. However, the lack of texts associated with these mosques makes it impossible to definitively answer this question.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No grave goods have been recovered from the tombs, given that they have not been excavated. It should be noted that Swahili tombs had foreign (esp. Chinese) ceramics embedded in them, to indicate the cosmopolitan nature and wealth of the dead.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are tombs associated with the mosques, including the pillar tombs for which the Swahili are known.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: Tomb clusters associated with individual families may be present.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: The mosques are located close to houses in the city of Gedi.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that Allah was actually considered to live at this place. However, the lack of texts associated with these mosques makes it impossible to definitively answer this question.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: However, the site today is

Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits whose exact nature remains unknown are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied

remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: None

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– I don't know

Notes: There are supposed to be evil and ancestral spirits residing at the site at present. Whether rituals

occur to contact or propitiate these remains unknown. Presumably, when the city was occupied, Muslim rituals took place at the mosques.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: These have not been reported in the literature on the site produced thus far.

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Notes: Evil and ancestral spirits are said to live at Gedi to this day. How they interact with humans remains unknown. Practices and beliefs when the city of Gedi was actually occupied remain unknown.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Notes: Pilgrimages could have taken place in the past when the city was occupied. However, this remains unanswerable until more archaeological data is recovered.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: Feasting could have taken place when the city was occupied. However, this remains unanswerable until more archaeological data is recovered.

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Notes: Festivals could have taken place in the past, especially those associated with the Muslim calendar. Whether they take place in association with the spirits that are supposed to reside at the site at present is unknown.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that divination took place in the past, when the city was occupied, and in the present, in association with the spirits that are supposed to live at the site.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that healing took place in the past, when the city was occupied, and in the present, in association with the spirits that are supposed to live at the site.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– I don't know

Notes: In the past, imams may have been present full time to care for the mosques. At present, it is unknown whether full-time ritual specialists exist to cater to the spirits that live at the site.

Present part time

– I don't know

Notes: In the past, imams may have been present part time to care for the mosques. At present, it is unknown whether part-time ritual specialists exist to cater to the spirits that live at the site.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– I don't know

Notes: Imams generally tend to be male. However, given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, it is possible that female and other religious specialists were present at the mosques. The sex/gender of the current religious specialists who cater to the spirits that live at the site remains unknown.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether the religious specialists of the past (Imams and others) belonged to a specific ethnicity remains unknown as we don't have detailed records associated with Gedi. However, the current caretakers and ritual specialists catering to the spirits that live at the site in the present belong to the Giriama group.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

Notes: The Imams and other religious specialists of the past could have belonged to a specific class/caste. However, the current religious specialists belonging to the Giriama group could be specialists or part-time practitioners belonging to a specific class/caste. This remains unknown.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

Notes: The Imams and other religious specialists of the past could have been dedicated to the place for life. However, the current religious specialists belonging to the Giriama group could be specialists or part-time practitioners, only partly dedicated to the place. This remains unknown.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– I don't know

Notes: The Imams and other religious specialists of the past could have stratified in a hierarchical system. However, whether the current religious specialists belonging to the Giriama group are stratified in a hierarchical system remains unknown.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: A separate living space for religious specialists could have been maintained when the city was occupied, especially given the proximity of the mosques to houses in Gedi. Whether the current ritual caretakers of the site have special living spaces remains unknown.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: Whether Muslim religious specialists were trained at the site remains unknown, as is whether the site is used to train the current ritual experts in charge of the site.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: In the past, the mosques were part of the city of Gedi and would have been maintained. The site at present is maintained by the Giriama and the National Museums of Kenya.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Notes: A formal bureaucracy could have existed in the past, when the city was occupied. Whether a formal "bureaucracy" has been established by the Giriama caretakers of the site remains unknown

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Notes: The mosques could have controlled economic resources when the city was occupied. They are in ruin now and do not control economic resources.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: Community services could have been provided when Gedi was a living city. Whether the Giriama use the site today to provide services to their community at present remains unknown. The site serves as a tourist attraction, providing some money to local communities.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Non-religious writing could have been stored at the site. This remains unknown, as is whether the Giriama use the site today to store non-religious texts.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Qurans were likely used in the mosques, but there are no specially dedicated scriptures associated with this place.

Bibliography

General References

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